

RESULTS OF SOCIOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON THE APPLICATION OF THE DUAL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE TRAINING OF QUALIFIED ENGINEERS

Ismoil Norkobilovich Kodirov
Karshi State Technical University
Professor, Department of “Energy Engineering”,
Candidate of Physical and Mathematical Sciences
E-mail: godirovissiqlik@gmail.com

Annotation

The article presents information about the purpose of using the dual education system in training qualified engineers in higher education institutions, its advantages over the traditional education system, the prospects for its application in the education system of our republic, as well as the results of a sociological study on the use of the dual education system in training qualified engineers.

Key words: traditional and dual education system, dual education program, thematic sections of research, sociological research, enterprise, students.

**MALAKALI MUHANDISLAR TAYYORLASHDA DUAL TA'LIM TIZIMINI
QO'LLASHGA OID OLIB BORILGAN SOTSIOLOGIK TADQIQOTLAR
NATIJALARI**

Ismoil Norkobilovich Kodirov
Qarshi davlat texnika universiteti
“Energetika muhandisligi” kafedrası
professori, fizika-matematika fanlari nomzodi
E-mail: godirovissiqlik@gmail.com

Annotatsiya

Maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida malakali muhandislar tayyorlashda dual ta'lim tizimidan foydalanishning maqsadi, uning an'anaviy ta'lim tizimiga nisbatan afzalliklari va dual ta'lim tizimini Respublikamiz ta'lim tizimida u qo'llanilishining kelajagi hamda malakali muhandislar tayyorlashda dual ta'lim tizimini qo'llashga oid olib borilgan sotsiologik tadqiqotlar natijalari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: anʻanaviy va dual taʻlim tizimi, dual taʻlim dasturi, tadqiqotning tematik boʻlimlari, sotsiologik tadqiqotlar, korxonalar, talabalar

**РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ СОЦИОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПО ПРИМЕНЕНИЮ
ДУАЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ПОДГОТОВКЕ
КВАЛИФИЦИРОВАННЫХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ**

Annotatsiya

В статье представлена информация о цели использования дуальной системы образования при подготовке квалифицированных инженеров в высших учебных заведениях, ее преимуществах перед традиционной системой образования, перспективах ее применения в системе образования нашей республики, а также результаты социологического исследования по использованию дуальной системы образования при подготовке квалифицированных инженеров.

Ключевые слова: традиционная и дуальная система образования, программа дуального образования, тематические разделы исследований, социологические исследования, предприятие, студенты.

Introduction.

On June 20, 2024, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan held a video conference dedicated to the topic of “Priority tasks in improving the training of personnel in engineering fields and the activities of higher education institutions.” During the session, he emphasized the importance of innovation and engineering personnel in the country today and outlined key tasks to be implemented, including:

- An “Industry–Enterprise–University” chain will be established, in which each higher education institution will be assigned an industrial partner, and “Advanced Engineering Schools” will be opened at 10 universities across the republic.
- Departments will be established within partner enterprises of all engineering universities, and dual education will be introduced, among other initiatives.

To further develop the implementation of dual education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Cabinet of Ministers approved Regulation No. 163 dated March 29, 2021, “On measures to organize dual education in the system of vocational education,” which defines the procedure for introducing dual education within the vocational training system.

In addition, Regulation No. 14 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated January 16, 2025, “On measures to organize dual education in the system of higher education,” also approved the procedure for implementing dual education at the higher education level.

According to this decision, starting from the 2025/2026 academic year, a phased introduction of dual education in the higher education system will be launched. Among the key initiatives is the establishment of the “Kasb Egasi” (Skilled Professional) dual education system. Currently, work is underway to further develop legislation by studying international experience, introducing amendments, and improving regulatory documents governing the dual education system, which is regulated in our country based on the aforementioned legal acts.

Furthermore, in Uzbekistan, important steps are being taken to prepare qualified engineering personnel in the field of renewable energy sources. These include the development of a national plan and special programs, as well as the creation of a new system for training engineering personnel using dual education methods at higher and secondary specialized educational institutions[1,12].

Problems encountered in the implementation of dual education have been reviewed, revealing that this form of education may not always be universally applicable or effective[3,12]. However, to date, the methods of dual education and the methodological foundations and principles for its implementation have not been sufficiently studied, and scientific research in this area remains limited.

The possibilities for participation of future engineering personnel and employer enterprises in the implementation of dual education, as well as the involvement of these participants in self-assessment for the development of competencies under dual education conditions, have not been sufficiently studied and remain relevant issues.

Moreover, under dual education conditions, students have the opportunity to consciously acquire knowledge and skills based on the results of self-assessment. This facilitates the effective formation of personal and professional knowledge, experience, and competencies among students. As a result, instructors are better able to improve teaching methods and are tasked with developing comprehensive instructional programs for dual education based on the students’ acquired knowledge and experience.

Literature Review on the Topic. The dual education system is widely implemented in more than 60 countries, including Germany, China, the USA, South Korea, Denmark, France, Macedonia, Montenegro, Switzerland, the Netherlands, Austria, Serbia, Slovenia, and several Asian countries. It is considered one of the modern educational technologies and a core system of

instruction. This system integrates the learning process with practical experience, serving as a foundation for the high-quality training of qualified specialists in various sectors of industry [5]. As for the term "dual", it is derived from the Latin word *dualis*, meaning "twofold". Dualism refers to a doctrine that promotes the coexistence of irreconcilable states, principles, ways of thinking, worldviews, tendencies, and epistemological foundations. It is a form of pluralism. The term was introduced by German philosopher Christian Wolff (1679–1754). Dualism typically contrasts paired concepts such as the world of ideas versus the real world, and can be expressed in philosophical, religious, anthropological, and ethical forms [2].

L.V. Sidakova defines the dual education system as "an educational system that combines the academic activities of educational institutions with the operations of industrial enterprises" [3]. The dual education system can also be considered a well-coordinated structure between higher vocational education institutions and production companies aimed at training professionals with the qualifications required for specific occupations [4].

A deeper analysis of local and foreign literature reveals that the dual education model can be conceptualized as one in which theoretical training is conducted at educational institutions, while practical training is carried out at production enterprises [5]. Analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature shows that there are now sufficient answers to many of the emerging questions regarding the organization of dual education. Moreover, terms such as "dual education", "dual education program", and "dual instruction" have been clarified in their technical meanings [10–12].

Research Methodology. In the process of introducing the dual education system into the higher education institutions' curriculum, a number of challenges are encountered. One of the main difficulties lies in the insufficient preparedness of enterprises to provide educational training, particularly the absence of designated training sites within the enterprises themselves. Additional issues include the need to increase the price of produced goods, lack of funding for education, the development of content and methods for newly established dual education programs, the formulation of dual education principles and categories, shortage of equipment, insufficient financial support, and the need to conduct numerous activities within the framework of dual education.

The primary goal of implementing dual education is to ensure the comprehensive development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, provide employment opportunities for the population—especially youth and women—in large and small business sectors, reduce poverty,

and train highly qualified specialists in high-tech fields by integrating labor activities with education.

The objective of dual education is to train highly skilled industrial professionals in advanced technological fields.

Furthermore, the introduction of this dual education system aims to train mid-level personnel with modern vocational skills across all sectors of the economy, while creating broad opportunities to support youth in acquiring various professions and specializations. Through this system, young people not only receive education but also develop their professional competencies directly in real workplaces. One of the major problems faced by higher education institutions in training engineering personnel is the disconnect between theoretical and practical classes. These are not conducted in an integrated and coordinated manner, making it difficult for students to assimilate both aspects simultaneously. Another key issue is the gap between employers and the labor market. Implementing the dual education module in higher education has shown effective results in addressing this problem.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has taken measures to enhance its higher education system by gradually narrowing the gap between education and labor markets. This has been achieved by introducing state education standards and professional standards aligned with the future job functions of university graduates. Implementing such an educational model is possible through the use of the dual education system [5–12]. In conducting this research effectively, various methods were employed, including analysis of scientific-pedagogical literature related to the organization of dual education, comparative evaluation of the content of higher education curricula, sociological surveys on training qualified engineers within the dual education framework, and comparative and analytical methods.

Research Results and Discussion. It is well known that under dual education conditions, students must be adequately prepared for practical training, develop the skills to work with various objects, and be capable of gaining experience in activities and elements that have professional significance. This ensures that the training process supports students in mastering hands-on tasks and acquiring practical knowledge relevant to their future careers. The implementation of dual education in any educational institution involves a comprehensive preparatory process, representing a shift from traditional forms of instruction to a supplementary educational system. This transition requires the adoption of new norms, shaped by changes in societal self-awareness and driven by the needs and demands of a modern society that is prepared for development and

self-improvement.

The dual education system benefits all parties involved—industrial enterprises and organizations, students, and the state—by addressing their respective interests:

- **For industrial enterprises**, it presents an opportunity to train their own workforce, reduce the costs associated with recruitment, retraining, and employee adaptation;
- **For higher education institutions**, it facilitates the preparation of highly qualified and competitive specialists;
- **For students**, it increases their adaptability to real industrial environments and enhances their chances of successful employment in their field of specialization upon graduation;
- **For the state**, it provides an effective solution to the broader challenge of preparing skilled professionals for the national economy.

Given that training highly qualified engineering specialists through dual education in higher education institutions is one of the most pressing issues of our time, sociological research was conducted to assess the importance and relevance of demand for dual education.

Overview of the Research

- **Purpose:** To determine the effectiveness of professional competency development within the framework of dual education in comparison with the traditional education system.
- **Object of the study:** A group of 88 senior (3rd–4th year) students from a higher education institution.
- **Main target group:** Students enrolled in the dual education system (44 respondents).
- **Control group:** Students enrolled in the traditional education system (44 respondents).

The thematic structure of the research consists of the following components:

- General assessment and prospects of the dual education system;
- Development of students' professional competencies;
- Evaluation of the achievement of educational program objectives;
- Analysis of employment prospects.

The differences between traditional and dual education systems are also reflected in several areas such as: motivational components, levels of subjective control, students' value orientations, and the personal qualities formed during the learning process.

In order to explore the demand for the dual education system in training qualified engineering personnel, a student survey was conducted. The survey aimed to gather insights on student perspectives regarding dual education.

The first question in the survey was:

1. "Would you prefer to study under the dual education system in the organization of the learning process?" (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. "Would you like to study based on the dual education system in the organization of the educational process?" — Chart of survey results.

Figure 2. "Dual education is the future of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan."

Figure 2. Graph of the survey results for the question: “Dual education is the future of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan.”

According to the sociological survey conducted among student respondents for the question "Would you like to study under the dual education system in the organization of the educational process?":

Results regarding dual education: 94% of the students responded "YES", indicating a preference for studying under the dual education system, while 6% responded "NO".

Results regarding traditional education: 84% of students responded "YES", 10% responded "NO", and 6% responded "I find it difficult to answer" (Figure 1).

Similarly, based on the results of the sociological survey conducted among student respondents for the statement "Dual education is the future of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan":

Results regarding dual education: 86.9% of respondents answered "Fully agree", and 13.1% answered "Agree".

Results regarding traditional education: 52.5% of students responded "Fully agree", 34.5% responded "Agree", 6.5% answered "Do not fully agree", and 6.5% answered "I find it difficult to agree" (Figure 2).

Conclusions:

1. The majority of respondents positively evaluated the dual education system, indicating high demand and support for its implementation.
2. Students involved in dual education programs highly value the following achievements in terms of reaching the goals of the engineering vocational training curriculum:
 - The teaching process is closely aligned with production demands;
 - Complex theories are mastered through practice and solving real professional problems;
 - Employers can assess future specialists directly in real production environments.
3. Students in the dual education system are oriented toward employment in their field of specialization, while those in the traditional education system are more likely to consider changing professions.

Recommendations:

1. Based on the analysis of the practice of implementing dual education in the training of qualified engineers, it is advisable to improve the legal and regulatory framework for its further development.

2. Students and graduates should be involved in the assessment of the dual education system, with special attention paid to developing their competencies through self-assessment and improvement of the dual education model.
3. In order to ensure the successful development of competencies, it is crucial to implement the principles of organizing dual education and to continue scientific research aimed at enhancing teaching methods based on the dual education model.

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